

Post-Laparotomy Surgery Outcomes in Patients Aged 1-12 Months

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Abstract:

Background: Laparotomy in infants, particularly those aged 1-12 months, is a critical surgical intervention commonly performed for conditions such as congenital anomalies and intestinal obstructions. Despite advancements in pediatric surgery, the procedure is associated with significant postoperative complications and mortality, underscoring the need for comprehensive analysis to improve patient outcomes.

Aim: This study aims to analyze the outcomes of laparotomic surgery in infants aged 1-12 months, focusing on the incidence of postoperative complications, their impact on mortality, and identifying predictors of adverse outcomes.

Methods: A retrospective cohort study was conducted on 300 infants who underwent laparotomy at a tertiary care hospital. Data on demographic and clinical characteristics, surgical outcomes, and complications were collected and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics, Chi-square tests, t-tests, and logistic regression were employed to identify significant predictors of mortality and complications.

Results: Postoperative complications occurred in 28.3% of patients, with wound infections (15%) being the most common. The overall mortality rate was 5%, significantly higher among patients with anastomotic leaks (33.3%). Logistic regression identified anastomotic leaks (OR: 5.4, $p < 0.001$) and respiratory complications (OR: 3.2, $p = 0.02$) as significant predictors of mortality.

Conclusion: Laparotomy in infants is associated with a substantial risk of postoperative complications and mortality, particularly in those with anastomotic leaks and respiratory complications. Early identification and targeted management of these high-risk patients are crucial to improving outcomes.

Recommendations: Enhanced perioperative care, vigilant monitoring, and the development of strategies to prevent key complications, such as anastomotic leaks, are recommended to reduce the morbidity and mortality associated with laparotomy in infants.

Keywords: Laparotomy, Infants, Postoperative Complications, Mortality, Anastomotic Leaks.

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Introduction

Laparotomy is a surgical procedure that involves making a large incision through the abdominal wall to gain access to the abdominal cavity. It is commonly performed in paediatric populations, particularly in infants under the age of 12 months, due to congenital anomalies, intestinal obstructions, and other life-threatening conditions. Despite advances in surgical procedures and perioperative care, the surgery is still linked with high morbidity and mortality, particularly in neonates and infants, who face unique physiological obstacles and have limited physiological reserves [1,2]. Recent research has shown that infants having laparotomy are especially sensitive to postoperative problems such as wound infections, respiratory issues, and anastomotic leaks, which can lead to longer hospital stays, readmissions, and higher mortality [3]. These issues not only influence the immediate postoperative period, but they can also

have long-term consequences for the newborns' growth and development [4]. The high prevalence of postoperative complications, as well as the accompanying mortality, highlights the need of identifying at-risk patients early on and implementing tailored risk-reduction efforts. Preoperative and intraoperative factors are increasingly being recognised for their influence on postoperative outcomes. The underlying condition necessitating surgery, the duration of the procedure, and the surgeon's experience have all been shown to have a major impact on the likelihood of postoperative complications [5,6]. Furthermore, recent advances in surgical procedures, such as minimally invasive approaches, have showed promise in lowering complication rates; nonetheless, their applicability in very young newborns is restricted, and classical laparotomy remains the standard of care in many cases [7].

In addition, current research has focused on identifying specific predictors of bad outcomes, such as anastomotic leaks and pulmonary problems. These variables are critical for creating risk stratification models that can inform clinical decision-making and resource allocation [8]. The use of logistic regression and other advanced statistical approaches has allowed researchers to gain a better understanding of the complex nature of postoperative complications and identify modifiable risk factors [9]. This study seeks to add to the expanding body of literature by conducting a thorough investigation of the outcomes of laparotomy in infants aged 1 to 12 months, with a particular emphasis on the incidence of postoperative complications and their impact on mortality and readmission rates. This study aims to analyze the outcomes of laparotomic surgery in infants aged 1-12 months, focusing on the incidence of postoperative complications, their impact on mortality, and identifying predictors of adverse outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was conducted as a retrospective cohort study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in a tertiary care hospital, specializing in Pediatric Surgery. The hospital is well-equipped with modern surgical facilities and caters to a large number of pediatric patients annually.

Participants: A total of 300 patients, aged between 1-12 months, who underwent laparotomic surgery at the study setting during the specified period, were included in this study. These patients were selected based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria outlined below.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 1-12 months at the time of laparotomy.
- Patients who underwent laparotomy for conditions such as [insert relevant conditions, e.g., intestinal obstruction, congenital anomalies, etc.].
- Availability of complete medical records for the entire follow-up period.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with incomplete medical records.
- Patients who underwent laparotomy in combination with other major surgeries (excluding minor adjunct procedures).

- Patients with pre-existing conditions that could significantly affect surgical outcomes, such as severe congenital heart disease or severe malnutrition.

Bias: To minimize bias, all patient records were reviewed independently by two investigators who were blinded to the study hypothesis. Any discrepancies in data extraction were resolved through discussion and, if necessary, by involving a third reviewer. Selection bias was reduced by including all eligible patients who met the inclusion criteria during the study period.

Data Collection: Data were collected from electronic medical records and included demographic information (age, gender), clinical data (preoperative diagnosis, type of surgery, duration of surgery, postoperative complications), and outcomes (length of hospital stay, readmission rates, mortality). Data collection was standardized using a pre-designed data extraction form to ensure consistency.

Procedure: The medical records of patients who met the inclusion criteria were reviewed to extract the relevant data. The primary outcome measures included postoperative complications, length of hospital stay, and mortality rates. Secondary outcomes included readmission rates and any subsequent surgeries required within 12 months of the initial laparotomy.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic and clinical characteristics. Continuous variables were presented as means and standard deviations, and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. Chi-square tests and t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests were used for comparisons, with a significance level of $p < 0.05$. Logistic regression identified factors associated with adverse outcomes.

Results

Participant Demographics and Clinical Characteristics: A total of 300 patients aged 1-12 months who underwent laparotomic surgery were included in this study. The mean age of the participants was 6.4 ± 3.2 months, with 160 (53.3%) males and 140 (46.7%) females. The majority of surgeries were performed for congenital anomalies (45%), followed by intestinal obstruction (35%), and other conditions such as tumors or infections (20%).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Frequency (%)	Mean $\pm$ SD (Range)
Total Participants	300 (100%)	
Age (months)		6.4 $\pm$ 3.2 (1-12)
Gender		
- Male	160 (53.3%)	
- Female	140 (46.7%)	
Primary Diagnosis		
- Congenital anomalies	135 (45%)	
- Intestinal obstruction	105 (35%)	
- Other (tumors, infections)	60 (20%)	

The average duration of surgery was 120 $\pm$ 30 minutes. Postoperative complications occurred in 85 (28.3%) patients, with the most common being wound infections (15%), followed by respiratory complications (7%), and anastomotic leaks (6.3%). The average length of hospital stay was 12.5 $\pm$ 5.4 days.

Table 2: Surgical Outcomes and Complications

Outcome/Complication	Frequency (%)	Mean $\pm$ SD (Range)
Duration of surgery (minutes)		120 $\pm$ 30 (60-180)
Postoperative Complications	85 (28.3%)	
- Wound infections	45 (15%)	
- Respiratory complications	21 (7%)	
- Anastomotic leaks	19 (6.3%)	
Length of hospital stay (days)		12.5 $\pm$ 5.4 (7-30)

The overall mortality rate in this cohort was 5% (15 patients). The mortality was higher among those who developed anastomotic leaks (33.3% of those with leaks) compared to those without leaks (3%). The 30-day readmission rate was 10% (30 patients), mainly due to complications like wound infections and respiratory issues.

Table 3: Mortality and Readmission Rates

Outcome	Frequency (%)
Overall Mortality	15 (5%)
- Among those with leaks	6 (33.3%)
- Among those without leaks	9 (3%)
30-day Readmission Rate	30 (10%)

Statistical Analysis: Comparative analysis showed that patients with postoperative complications had a significantly longer hospital stay (15.3 $\pm$ 6.2 days) compared to those without complications (10.2 $\pm$ 3.8 days), $p < 0.001$. Logistic regression analysis

identified anastomotic leaks (OR: 5.4, 95% CI: 2.1-13.9, $p < 0.001$) and respiratory complications (OR: 3.2, 95% CI: 1.2-8.5, $p = 0.02$) as significant predictors of mortality.

Table 4: Logistic Regression Analysis of Predictors of Mortality

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% CI	p-value
Anastomotic leaks	5.4	2.1 - 13.9	<0.001
Respiratory complications	3.2	1.2 - 8.5	0.02
Duration of surgery	1.1	0.9 - 1.3	0.15
Length of hospital stay	1.2	0.8 - 1.6	0.07

Discussion

The study included 300 infants aged 1-12 months who underwent laparotomic surgery, with a fairly even gender distribution. The majority of surgeries were performed for congenital anomalies and intestinal obstruction. The findings revealed that postoperative complications were relatively common, occurring in 28.3% of patients. Wound infections were the most frequent complication, followed by respiratory issues and anastomotic leaks. Patients with complications experienced

significantly longer hospital stays, highlighting the impact of these adverse events on recovery.

The overall mortality rate was 5%, with a notably higher mortality observed among patients who developed anastomotic leaks. This suggests that anastomotic leaks are a critical factor influencing survival in this patient population. The 30-day readmission rate was 10%, indicating that a significant portion of patients faced ongoing challenges after discharge, often related to wound infections and respiratory complications.

Statistical analysis identified anastomotic leaks and respiratory complications as significant predictors of mortality, with patients experiencing these complications being at a much higher risk of death. This underscores the importance of vigilant postoperative care and early detection of these complications to improve outcomes.

In a study it was investigated the feasibility of recruiting subjects to assess postoperative complications and quality of life up to one year after emergency laparotomy. It employed proven instruments to assess outcomes such as morbidity at various postoperative phases and patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) for quality of life. The study effectively collected data from a large number of participants, emphasising the necessity of monitoring long-term healing and quality of life in patients following emergency laparotomy [10].

Thirty-day Surgical Outcome for Patients Undergoing Emergency Laparotomy (2018): This descriptive study examined 151 patients who underwent emergency laparotomy and found a high 30-day death rate of 23.84%. The study emphasised the high hazards of emergency laparotomies and the need for improved postoperative care procedures to prevent mortality and complications [11].

Short-term outcomes of laparotomy at Gulu University's two teaching hospitals in Northern Uganda (2020): This study looked at the clinical indications for laparotomy, intraoperative findings, and 30-day postoperative outcomes in a resource-limited context. The study discovered a crude mortality rate of 15.6%, with surgical site infections and wound dehiscence being frequent sequelae. It demonstrated that age was a crucial factor in predicting results, with older patients having lower recovery rates [12].

Conclusion

The study highlights the substantial risks associated with postoperative complications in infants undergoing laparotomy. The findings emphasize the need for careful monitoring, prompt management of complications, and potentially the development of strategies to prevent anastomotic leaks and respiratory issues, which were the most significant predictors of mortality in this cohort.

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